

EFFECTIVENESS OF ROOF STIFFENING BARS FOR UPGRADING LATERAL TORSIONAL BUCKLING CAPACITY OF ARCHES COMPOSED OF H-SECTIONS

Someta SOR*, Shiro KATO^a, Shoji NAKAZAWA^a, Nariaki HONDAYAMA^b, Toshihiko IJIMA^b

* Nakanihon Engineering Consultant

1-16-15 Marunouchi, Naka Ward, Nagoya City, zip code 460-0002, Japan
 s_sor@nakanihon.co.jp

^a Toyohashi University of Technology

^b Iijima Structural Design Office

Abstract

The present study discusses the effectiveness of roof stiffening bars for enhancing buckling strength of an arch subjected to uniform and non-uniform loads, followed by a proposal for an evaluation method of buckling strength. The study assumes that the arch is composed of H-600x200x9x16 steel members. A new FEM line element is introduced to include the lateral torsional effects of the H-sections on buckling. The analyzed arch is categorized into four cases, each with different lateral stiffening positions along the arch length: upper flange and/or lower flange of the H-sections. Based on the analysis results, a buckling strength evaluation method is proposed, enhancing the design flexibility of spatial structures. The necessity of the new FEM line element for compound buckling in lateral torsional buckling analysis is confirmed. Additionally, the practicality of an approximate-beam element for compound buckling is also validated as an alternative method to the new FEM line element in lateral torsional buckling analysis.

Keywords: arch structure, H-section, global buckling, lateral torsional buckling, warping deformation, buckling stiffener.

1. Introduction

A pioneering study on out-of-plane buckling of arches, which are fundamental frameworks for large-span roofs, was conducted in early stages by Uchiyama *et al.* [1]. This study analyzed the linear buckling load of an arch under vertical loads, considering flexural-torsional deformation, while assuming the cross-section of members is rectangular. Subsequent research on the in-plane elasto-plastic buckling of flat arches composed of tubular section, under both uniform and non-uniform loads, was conducted by Kamimura *et al.* [2], Yamashita *et al.* [3, 4], and Higuchi *et al.* [5]. These studies confirmed that, under uniform loading, global buckling occurs at half the arch length, and members of the arch reach the buckling strength almost without yielding. They also highlighted that the arch has relatively low sensitivity to initial imperfections. On the other hand, under non-uniform loading, plastic hinges formed at one-quarter of the arch length when reaching the buckling strength. Kamimura *et al.* [2] also emphasized the risk of out-of-plane buckling due to the weak-axis bending stiffness of members at the joints. Yamashita *et al.* [3, 4] and Higuchi *et al.* [5] discussed approximate methods for estimating the strength of arches composed of tubular section, considering the bending resistance of the members. AIJ recommendation [6] also introduced a calculation method for such arches. In particular, Yamashita *et al.* [4] proposed an imperfection-equivalent-antisymmetric-coefficient to account for the increase in bending moment due to initial imperfections. Deguchi *et al.* [7], through parametric analyses of elasto-plastic buckling of tubular section arches under uniform loads, confirmed that the flat arches generally exhibit elastic buckling with the buckling length approximately equal to half the arch length. They also confirmed that for the arches with half open angle of 25 degrees or more, the knock down factor for initial imperfections of 1/1000 of an arch span is approximately 0.90. They also provided average values

of strength and coefficients of variation, offering basic data for reliability analysis. While these data are valuable for calculating the strength of tubular section arches, there are few researches on the effects of buckling stiffeners installed in arches and roofs composed of H-section.

Given the limited data on the buckling behavior of H-section arches, this paper examines the buckling strength of an H-section arch, as a case study, with a span of approximately 60 meters and a rise of 5 meters. The study focuses on out-of-plane flexural-torsional buckling, investigating how the arrangement of stiffeners along the arch length influences the buckling loads. Based on the results of the analyses, an approximate method for evaluating buckling strength is proposed. In particular, the study explores the effects of stiffeners positioned at various locations along the arch length on mitigating the risk of flexural-torsional buckling. The analyses utilize a newly developed FEM element by Kato *et al.* [8, 9], referred to as the composite buckling element, which incorporates the effects of warping deformation in H-sections. Additionally, the paper also provides buckling analysis results obtained using an alternative method, the approximate-beam element proposed by Sor *et al.* [10].

Figure 1: Geometry of arch structure

2. Geometry of arch structure

Shape: Figure 1 shows an arch with a half open angle of $\phi_0=20^\circ$. The radius of curvature, arch span, and rise are defined based on the position of the lower flange, with the values of $R=85.96$ m, $L=58.80$ m, and $H_z=5.18$ m, respectively.

Arch support: The arch is supported by pins at both ends, and out-of-plan displacements are restrained.

Member: The arch is constructed by connecting 10 members of H-600x200x9x16 section, each with a length of 6.0 m. The Young's modulus is $E=205000$ N/mm², and the yield stress is $\sigma_y=235$ N/mm². The cross-sectional area is $A=11510$ mm², with the second moments of area around the weak and strong axes being $I_z=2137 \times 10^4$ mm⁴ and $I_y=68326 \times 10^4$ mm⁴, respectively. The yield axial force and plastic moment capacity are $N_y=2705$ kN and $M_p=609.75$ kNm, respectively. The radius of gyration around the strong axis is $r_{gy}=243.6$ mm, and the slenderness ratio for half the arch length of 30.0 m is $\lambda_y=124$. The radius of gyration around the weak axis is $r_{gz}=43.1$ mm, with a slenderness ratio for the member length of 6.0 m being $\lambda_z=139$. If out-of-plane stiffening is sufficient, the buckling load will be determined by in-plane buckling. The equivalent plate thickness is $2\sqrt{3}r_{gy}=844$ mm.

Modeling of members: Each 6.0-meter-long H-section is modelled with six composite buckling elements (by Kato *et al.* [8, 9]) in equal length. These elements, as shown in Figure 2, consist of upper flange, web, and lower flange, which are further supported by four rigid axial and bending strut members.

Modeling of Joints: At the joints, as shown in Figure 4, two H-sections are connected at an angle to form a planar triangle. The upper and lower flanges are joined by a diaphragm (stiffed panel), while the

webs are welded to the adjacent webs, providing a sufficiently rigid connection. Adjacent upper flanges are connected by a rigid member P_AQ_A , while adjacent webs are similarly joined by a rigid member P_CQ_C . At the lower flange position, adjacent flanges at the same coordinates (P_B , Q_B) are constrained to have the same displacement. The connection members P_AQ_A and P_CQ_C , along with the four strut members P_AP_C , P_CP_B , Q_AQ_C , Q_CQ_B , are designed to ensure rigid body displacement with sufficient axial and bending stiffness at the joints. However, the Saint-Vernant torsional constant J for the strut members P_AP_C and P_CP_B are set to zero, allowing independent warping of the H-sections when deformation occurs in the upper and lower flanges on the left side. The same applies to the strut members Q_AQ_C and Q_CQ_B on the right side.

Figure 2: Composite buckling element

Figure 3: Loading conditions

Figure 4: Modeling of joints

Loads condition: The arch is assumed to be spaced at 3.0 m intervals, and the loads are applied vertically. The dead load per unit length of the arch is 3.00 kN/m, and the uniform snow load per roof area is 3.36 kN/m². To account for non-uniform snow loading, the right half of the arch is assumed to carry half of the uniform snow load on the left half. As shown in Figure 3, the loads at the midpoint of the upper flange and at the webs on both ends are denoted as $P_{0(m)}$ and $P_{0(n)}$, respectively. The equivalent load per node is defined as $P_{0eq} = P_{0(m)} + 2P_{0(n)}$. During snow loading, the equivalent load per node on the left side of the arch is ${}_L P_{0eq} = 38.16$ kN, calculated as 19.08 kN + 19.08 kN = 38.16 kN. For the buckling analysis, one-tenth of this value, ${}_F P_{0eq} = 3.816$ kN, is used as the basic load. On the right side of the arch, the corresponding basic load is ${}_{FR} P_{0eq} = 3.816$ kN for uniform snow loading and ${}_{FR} P_{0eq} = 2.808$ kN for non-uniform snow loading.

Stiffening Position: As shown in Figure 5, four cases of stiffening — A, B, C, and D — are analyzed for the out-of-plane buckling of the arch. Lateral deformation (out-of-plane) at the positions marked with a circle is assumed to be restrained against out-of-plane translations by truss members or similar components. In stiffening cases A, C, and D, lateral stiffening is applied to the upper flange at the midpoint of the 6.0-meter-long members, spaced at 3.0-meter intervals, with the assumption that purlins or similar components are connected at these positions.

Initial Imperfection: Under non-uniform loads, based on the observation [3, 4, 5] that the bending moment increases at the quarter-point positions of the arch in collapse procedures, initial imperfections

are introduced at member 3 and member 8 for both stiffening cases A and B. For stiffening cases C and D, which involves relatively long stiffening intervals, initial imperfections are assumed at positions with the longest stiffening interval. Figure 5 shows the distribution of these initial imperfections. For all stiffening cases, the value of δ_i is determined based on the stiffening interval l_{br} , with δ_i defined as $\delta_i = l_{br}/1000$. The initial imperfections are assumed to be uniform across the web, upper and lower flanges.

- **Stiffening case A and B:** The amplitude δ_i of the initial imperfection is set for member 3, and $-\delta_i$ for member 8. The waveform of these two members is assumed to follow a half-sine wave.
- **Stiffening case C:** The initial imperfections are applied between members 3 and 5, and between members 6 and 8. The maximum amplitudes of δ_i and $-\delta_i$ are taken at the midpoints of members 4 and 6, respectively. The waveform is assumed to have a triangular shape.
- **Stiffening case D:** The amplitude δ_i increases linearly between members 1 and 2, reaches its maximum and remains constant for member 3, and decreases linearly between members 4 and 5, forming a trapezoidal shape. For members 6 to 10, the initial imperfections are set to be antisymmetric to those of members 1 to 5.

Figure 5: Loading conditions

3. Internal forces of arch under basic load

In this section, linear elastic analysis of the arch under the basic load $rP_{0eq}=3.816$ kN is performed to find resultant forces. However, due to space limitation, detailed results are omitted. Since the analysis does not account for initial imperfections, no out-of-plane deformations occur in the members.

3.1. Internal forces of arch under uniform load

Under uniform load, the internal forces in all members remain relatively constant throughout the arch, while the bending moments are notably low. The maximum axial force of 56.4 kN occurs in member 1, and the minimum axial force of 53.5 kN is observed in member 5. The maximum bending moment of 3.0 kNm occurs at the midpoint of member 5.

3.2. Internal forces of arch under non-uniform load

Under non-uniform load, significant bending moments occur at the quarter point of the arch. In the upper flange, the bending moments cause compressions on the left half of the arch, and tensions on the right half side. However, the axial force remains nearly constant all along the span. The average axial force across the ten members is 47.4 kN, approximately 0.87 times the average axial force of 54.7 kN under uniform loading. The ratio of the total non-uniform loads to the total uniform loads is calculated as $(2.808+3.816)/2/3.816=0.87$, demonstrating that the axial forces are generally proportional to the total loads on the arch.

4. Linear buckling analysis

The linear buckling loads under the basic load $FP_{0eq}=3.816$ kN are converted into equivalent nodal loads and presented as $LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM)$ in Table 1, where the subscript “(FEM)” indicates results derived from the composite buckling elements (as proposed by Kato *et al.* [8, 9]). Initial imperfections are assumed to be zero. The linear buckling load factor $\lambda_{cr}^{lin}(FEM)$ is calculated using the following equation:

$$\lambda_{cr}^{lin}(FEM) = LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM) / FP_{0eq} \quad (1)$$

Since this factor can be derived directly from $LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM)$, it is not listed in Table 1. The linear buckling loads represent the lowest value among several possible buckling modes. Although not shown, variations in the magnitude of initial imperfections do not affect the linear buckling load $LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM)$.

Figure 6 shows the lowest buckling modes under non-uniform loads. Although the buckling modes under uniform loads are not shown, for stiffening case B, C, and D, the arch buckles with a small buckling wave length similarly to the left side of the buckled arch under non-uniform loads. In contrast, the arch of stiffening case A results in global buckling, similarly to the behavior observed commonly under uniform and non-uniform loads, however, the effective buckling length under non-uniform loads is somewhat longer than that under uniform loads.

Table 1: Buckling loads of arch (kN); initial imperfections $\delta_i=l_{br}/1000$.
(The superscript * denotes the buckling length due to global buckling of the arch.)

		Under uniform loads				Under non-uniform loads			
		case A	case B	case C	case D	case A	case B	case C	case D
Stiffening interval l_{br} (cm)		600	600	1800	3000	600	600	1800	3000
Buckling loads of arch obtained from composite buckling element	$LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM)$	106.2	86.1	83.6	59.9	122.4	92.0	65.6	42.7
	$LP_{eqcr}^{el}(FEM)$	103.4	84.8	79.3	56.4	84.7	68.6	50.5	39.6
	$LP_{eqcr}(FEM)$	103.6	80.8	79.4	57.9	65.8	59.1	48.6	37.2
	l_{cr} (cm)	2968*	583	592	847	2956*	608	714	884
Evaluation of buckling strength based on maximum axial force ($\alpha_0=1.0$)	Member No.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	$DLP_{eqcr}(N)$	83.8	72.7	71.4	54.6	96.5	78.8	57.1	37.1
	Λ	1.31	1.46	1.48	1.75	1.31	1.51	1.79	2.21
Evaluation of buckling strength based on strength interaction of axial force and bending moment ($\alpha_0=1.0$)	Member No.	1	1	4	1	3	3	1	3
	$DLP_{eqcr}(N, M)$	79.6	69.7	68.2	52.7	72.9	63.7	53.5	36.9
	LP_{eqpl}	159.1	159.1	156.2	159.1	114.8	114.8	114.8	114.8
	Λ_s	1.22	1.36	1.37	1.66	0.97	1.12	1.55	1.64
Evaluation of buckling: strength interaction of axial force and bending moment	$\alpha_0=0.90$	—	—	—	—	69.6	62.0	46.4	35.0
	$\alpha_0=0.80$	—	—	—	—	65.7	56.0	42.5	31.6
	$\alpha_0=0.75$	—	—	—	—	63.5	53.9	40.4	29.9
Approximate beam element	$LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(\text{approx})$	105.1	86.5	85.0	59.5	121.0	93.8	70.0	46.7

Figure 6: Linear buckling modes of the arch under non-uniform loads

4.1. Linear buckling analysis under uniform loads

Stiffening case A: The arch undergoes global buckling, and the effective buckling length l_{cr} for this case is approximately half the length of the arch, as determined by the following equation. Here, I_y represents the second moment of area around the strong axis, and $N_{0(N)}=56.4$ kN.

$$l_{cr} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 EI_y}{N_{0(N)} \lambda_{cr(FEM)}^{lin}}} \quad (2)$$

Stiffening case B: The buckling mode resembles the Euler buckling of members, with slight torsion. Both the upper and lower flanges are displaced in the weak axis direction (out-of-plane) over the stiffening interval $l_{br}=6.0$ m. The equivalent buckling length l_{cr} for this case is approximately equal to the member length $l_0=6.0$ m, as determined by the following equation, where I_z represents the moment of area around the weak axis.

$$l_{cr} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 EI_z}{N_{0(N)} \lambda_{cr(FEM)}^{lin}}} \quad (3)$$

Stiffening case C: The displacement in the weak axis direction of the upper flange is minimal, whereas the lower flange exhibits significant displacement, resulting in flexural-torsional buckling. The equivalent buckling length l_{cr} , calculated using Equation (3), is notably smaller than the stiffening interval $l_{br}=18.0$ m. This reduction is attributed to the restraint at the upper flange at multiple nodes.

Stiffening case D: Similarly to stiffening case C, the upper flange experiences minimal displacement in the weak axis direction, while the lower flange undergoes significant displacement, resulting in flexural-torsional buckling. The equivalent buckling length l_{cr} is significantly smaller than the stiffening interval $l_{br}=30.0$ m, due to the restraining effect at multiple nodes at the upper flange.

Without warping deformation: Where Saint-Venant torsional constant of strut ST in the composite buckling elements is set to $J=6830 \times 10^4$ mm⁴, the result shows that the linear buckling loads of stiffening case C and D are approximately the same as that of stiffening case A. On the other hand, for stiffening case B, LP_{eqcr}^{lin} is 86.2 kN, nearly identical to the 86.1 kN obtained when $J=0$ mm⁴. This is due to member 3 undergoing weak-axis Euler buckling with almost no torsional deformation.

4.2. Linear buckling under non-uniform loads

Stiffening case A through D: The average linear buckling loads of the left and right sides of the arch under non-uniform loads in stiffening cases A, B, C, and D are 106.1 kN, 79.8 kN, 57.6 kN, and 37.5 kN, respectively. In comparison to cases under uniform loads of 106.2 kN, 86.1 kN, 83.6 kN, and 59.9 kN, the buckling loads for stiffening cases C and D under non-uniform loads show a significant decrease.

Without warping deformation: Where Saint-Venant torsional constant of strut ST in the composite buckling elements is set to $J=6830 \times 10^4$ mm⁴, the linear buckling loads of stiffening cases C and D are identical to that of stiffening case A with $LP_{eqcr}^{lin}=122.4$ kN. In these cases, the lateral displacement of the upper flange at the center of each member is restrained, making the effect of the torsional constant in the strut members significant. On the other hand, in stiffening case B, $LP_{eqcr}^{lin(FEM)}$ is 97.6 kN, only slightly higher than the 92.0 kN when $J=0$ mm⁴. This is attributed to the absence of torsional deformation and the occurrence of weak-axis Euler buckling, similarly to that under uniform loading condition.

Under both uniform and non-uniform loads, the linear buckling loads of the arch in stiffening cases C and D significantly differ between $J=0$ mm⁴ and $J=6830 \times 10^4$ mm⁴. Therefore, it can be concluded that conventional beam elements, which do not account for warping deformation, are not suitable for this case of applications.

5. Elastic and elasto-plastic buckling analysis

This section analyses elastic and elasto-plastic buckling loads. The buckling loads obtained from elastic and elasto-plastic buckling analyses, denoted as $LP_{eqcr}^{el}(FEM)$ and $LP_{eqcr}(FEM)$, respectively, are presented in Table 1.

5.1. Elastic and elasto-plastic buckling under uniform load

Under uniform loads, for initial imperfection of $\delta_i=l_{br}/1000$, the values of $LP_{eqcr}(FEM)$, $LP_{eqcr}^{el}(FEM)$, and $LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM)$ are approximately the same. It is observed that, for all stiffening cases, the buckling strength generally remains within the elastic range, and $LP_{eqcr}(FEM)$ can be regarded as elastic buckling load.

For stiffening case A, which involves global buckling, the knock down factor α_0 , accounting for weak axis initial imperfection of $\delta_i=l_{br}/1000$, is calculated as:

$$\alpha_0 = LP_{eqcr}^{el}(FEM) / LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM) \quad (4)$$

This factor is 0.97, indicating that the impact of weak axis initial imperfections on global buckling is less significant compared to the 0.945 reported by Deguchi *et al.* [7]. For the other stiffening cases, α_0 is 0.98 for stiffening case B, 0.95 for stiffening case C, and 0.94 for stiffening case D. These results suggest that the knock down factor α_0 due to weak axis initial imperfections is generally about 0.95 for weak axis buckling.

5.2. Elastic buckling and elasto-plastic buckling under non-uniform load

Under non-uniform loads, in all stiffening cases A through D, $LP_{eqcr}^{el}(FEM)$ is lower than $LP_{eqcr}^{lin}(FEM)$, where weak axis buckling occurs. The knock down factor α_0 , calculated using Equation (4), results in the values of 0.69, 0.75, 0.77, and 0.93 for stiffening cases A, B, C, and D, respectively, highlighting that the sensitivity to initial imperfections is somewhat lower in stiffening D. Additionally, $LP_{eqcr}(FEM)$ of all the stiffening cases A to D are smaller than $LP_{eqcr}^{el}(FEM)$, and the reduction ratios of the latter to the former are 0.78, 0.86, 0.96, and 0.94 respectively. This reduction is due to both effects of the pre-buckling deformation and yielding of the sections.

Due to space limitations, the load-displacement curves are excluded. In stiffening case C, significant lateral displacement along the weak axis begins between members 5, 6, and 7 at relatively low load levels, accompanied by torsional deformation. The load-to-vertical displacement curve indicates that, up to near the maximum load, the behavior of stiffening case C is almost the same to that of stiffening case A. However, due to initial imperfections, the lateral displacement of lower flange at midpoint of member 7 increases prior to reaching the maximum load. This significant lateral displacement along the weak axis between members 5, 6, and 7 leads to yielding in the lower flanges. As weak axis deformation involving torsion continues to intensify, the increase in load capacity nearly halts. In stiffening case D, the behavior closely resembles that of stiffening case C, where weak-axis deformation combined with torsion dominates as the primary failure mode, leading to an even lower buckling load.

6. Buckling strength evaluation

This section discusses two approaches for evaluating the buckling strength of the arch, based on the AIJ Recommendation [11, 12].

6.1. Buckling strength evaluation using axial force of specific member

According to the AIJ Recommendation [11], the buckling strength of the arch can be evaluated using Dunkerley's equation. The buckling strength, denoted as $DL P_{eqcr(N)}$, is evaluated by Equation (5).

$$DL P_{eqcr(N)} = N_{0(N)} \times {}_D \lambda_{cr}, \quad \left(\frac{N_{0(N)}}{N_y} \right) \lambda_{pl} = 1, \quad \Lambda = \sqrt{\frac{N_y}{\alpha_0 N_{0(N)} \lambda_{cr}^{lin}(FEM)}}, \quad \frac{{}_D \lambda_{cr}}{\lambda_{pl}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\Lambda^4 + 4 + \Lambda^2}} \quad (5)$$

6.1.1. Under uniform loads

Based on the linear elastic analysis under the basic load $F P_{0eq}=3.816$ kN, the axial force $N_{0(N)}$ for member 1 (specific member) is 56.4 kN. The linear buckling load factor, λ_{cr}^{lin} (FEM), for $F P_{0eq}=3.816$ kN is calculated using Equation (1). Table 1 presents the values of $DL P_{eqcr(N)}$ calculated with $\alpha_0=1.0$. For initial imperfection of $\delta_i=l_{br}/1000$, the ratio $LP_{eqcr(FEM)}/DL P_{eqcr(N)}$ of stiffening cases A, B, C, and D are 1.24, 1.11, 1.11, and 1.05, respectively. These ratios confirm a safe evaluation of $DL P_{eqcr(N)}$.

6.1.2. Under non-uniform loads

Using the axial force $N_0=49.3$ kN of member 1 (specific member) under non-uniform loads, the buckling load evaluation $DL P_{eqcr(N)}$, calculated using Equation (5) with $\alpha_0=1.0$, are presented in Table 1. The normalized slenderness ratio Λ_s ranges from 1.31 to 1.22, indicating that the buckling load falls within the elastic range. For initial imperfection of $\delta_i=l_0/1000$, the ratio $LP_{eqcr(FEM)}/DL P_{eqcr(N)}$ ranges between 0.68 to 1.00, suggesting that $DL P_{eqcr(N)}$ is overestimated. This overestimation can be attributed to the omission of bending moment effects and pre-buckling nonlinearity due to the assumption of $\alpha_0=1.0$.

Figure 7: Strength interaction of axial force and bending moment

6.2. Buckling strength evaluation based on the interaction of axial force and bending moment

According to AIJ Recommendation [12], the strength interaction of axial force N_0 and bending moment M_0 is represented by the dashed curve shown in Figure 7. This curve varies with the ratio A_f/A_w (the ratio of the flange's cross-sectional area to the web's cross-sectional area), but it can be approximated by two linear segments, assuming a small error when the axial force is very low. Assuming that the internal forces are proportional to the axial forces N_0 and bending moments M_0 obtained from linear elastic analysis, a member reaches its yield point when it satisfies the following plastic load factor λ_{pl} :

$$\left(\frac{N_0}{N_y} + \frac{M_0}{1.14M_p} \right) \lambda_{pl} = 1 \quad \text{when} \quad \left(\frac{N_0}{N_y} \right) / \left(\frac{M_0}{M_p} \right) \geq 0.1224 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{M_0}{M_p} \lambda_{pl} = 1 \quad \text{when} \quad \left(\frac{N_0}{N_y} \right) / \left(\frac{M_0}{M_p} \right) < 0.1224$$

The minimum value among the calculated λ_{pl} of all members of the arch is then adopted as λ_{pl} . Regardless of initial imperfections, the evaluated equivalent plastic load LP_{eqpl} remains the same for the selected member and is determined by the following equation:

$$LP_{eqpl} = \lambda_{pl} \times F P_{0eq} \quad (7)$$

The normalized slenderness ratio Λ_s is defined as follows:

$$\Lambda_s = \sqrt{\frac{L P_{eqpl}}{\alpha_0 L P_{eqcr}^{lin}}} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{pl}}{\alpha_0 \lambda_{cr}^{lin}}} \quad (8)$$

Then, the buckling strength evaluation, based on the strength interaction of the axial force and bending moment, can be carried out using the Dunkerley's equation and expressed as follows:

$${}_{DL}P_{eqcr(N,M)} = \frac{2 L P_{eqpl}}{\sqrt{\Lambda_s^4 + 4 + \Lambda_s^2}} \quad (9)$$

6.2.1. Under uniform loads

As shown in Table 1, $L P_{eqpl}$ is significantly larger than $L P_{eqcr}^{lin}{}_{(FEM)}$, and the normalized slenderness ratio Λ_s (when $\alpha_0=1.0$) exceeds 1.0, indicating elastic buckling behavior. As previously mentioned, under uniform loads with initial imperfection of $\delta_i=l_{br}/1000$, the strength of the arch remains within the elastic range. Using $\alpha_0=1.0$, the evaluation ${}_{DL}P_{eqcr(N,M)}$ is slightly lower than ${}_{DL}P_{eqcr(N)}$, but still safely evaluates the buckling strength $L P_{eqcr(FEM)}$ of the arch.

6.2.2. Under non-uniform loads

As confirmed in the previous section, the knock down factors for stiffening cases A, B, C, and D under non-uniform loads are 0.69, 0.75, 0.77, and 0.93, respectively. In addition to $\alpha_0=1.0$, cases with $\alpha_0=0.90$, 0.80, and 0.75 are also examined, and the results are presented in Table 1. With $\alpha_0=1.0$, the ratio ${}_{DL}P_{eqcr(N,M)}/L P_{eqcr(FEM)}$ for stiffening cases A, B, C, and D are 1.11, 1.08, 1.10, and 0.99, respectively, indicating a consistent overestimation of approximately 10% for stiffening cases A, B, and C. By considering the influence of bending moments, even with $\alpha_0=1.0$, the estimation accuracy improves compared to the method using only the axial force of a specific member. At $\alpha_0=0.80$, results are on the safe side for all stiffening cases. At $\alpha_0=0.75$, the ratios $L P_{eqcr(N,M)}/L P_{eqcr(FEM)}$ for stiffening cases A, B, C, and D are 0.97, 0.91, 0.83, and 0.80, respectively, indicating that the evaluation is safe.

The evaluation accuracy of the buckling strength improves by calculating the plastic load while accounting for the interaction of the axial force and bending moment. However, the choice of knock down factor α_0 depends on various factors, such as the size of the H-section, the half open angle of the arch, the degree of non-uniform loads, and the distribution of initial imperfections along the weak and strong axes. Therefore, further data accumulation will be necessary for future analyses.

7. Buckling analysis using approximate beam element

In this section, the approximate beam element proposed by Sor *et al.* [10] is used in the buckling analyses of the arch as an alternative. Similarly to the composite buckling element, the approximate beam element is composed of three conventional beam elements, enabling warping and torsional deformation of H-sections. The buckling loads of the arch obtained from this element are also presented in Table 1, where the subscript "(approx)" denotes the results derived from the approximate beam element.

Under both uniform and non-uniform loads, $L P_{eqcr}^{lin}{}_{(approx)}$ are nearly equal to $L P_{eqcr}^{lin}{}_{(FEM)}$ obtained from the composite buckling element. The buckling strength of the arch can be evaluated using an appropriate knock down factor α_0 along with the linear buckling loads, and the approximate beam element is confirmed efficient for linear buckling analysis for warping and torsional effects.

8. Conclusion

In the present buckling analysis, it has been demonstrated that the task of evaluating buckling while considering variations in stiffening positions is challenging when using the conventional beam element.

However, it has been confirmed that the composite buckling element is effective in examining the effects of such buckling stiffening. Additionally, a method for evaluating the buckling strength has been proposed, based on the Dunkerley's equation, which incorporates the strength interaction of the axial force and bending moment. It has been shown that the knock down factor α_0 of 0.75 or 0.80 allows for an approximate and safe evaluation of the buckling strength of the H-section arch, accounting for bending, warping, and torsional deformation. The application of the approximate beam element has also been demonstrated, and its accuracy in linear buckling analysis has been validated through comparison with the results obtained from the composite buckling element.

Subsequent studies are planned to further investigate the effects of buckling stiffening by examining various parameters, including the size of the H-sections, the half open angle of the arch, the degree of non-uniform loads, the initial imperfection shapes, and in-plane initial imperfections.

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